

INVESTIGATION ON THE FABRICATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS PREPARED THROUGH FILAMENT WINDING

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ABSTRACT

In the fabrication of composite materials prepared through filament winding, resin viscosity and fiber tension are two important processing parameters. This research presents the influence of these two parameters on mechanical properties of composite cylinders fabricated by filament winding. The material system includes glass/epoxy, carbon/epoxy, and hybrid reinforcement(carbon+glass)/epoxy. It is found that the higher the resin viscosity, the better the mechanical properties of composite cylinders made by these three material systems. For composite cylinders wound under fiber tension 15 N (Newton) and 50 N, the former has lower tensile strength than the latter when winding angle of 90 degree; however, a reverse result is observed when winding angle of 60 and 45 degree are adopted. On the compressive strength, the former is higher than the latter in all these three cases. Besides, it is found that hybrid composite cylinders show a medium strength in both tensile and compression tests as compared to glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy composite cylinders.

INTRODUCTION

Filament winding is a composite fabrication route which the fiber strands are impregnated with resin and wound onto a rotating mandrel in a predetermined fiber path under controlled tension. The wound part is further cured to form the composite. Because of the features of same orientation for continuous fibers and axisymmetrical configurations of mandrels, the filament wound composites have advantages of high specific strength and modulus, besides, they also have the benefits of low cost and various production configurations. On the investigation of processing parameters, Springer [1-3] established the relationships between the processing variables, such as winding speed, fiber tension and heating rate, and performance of semi-fabricated , such as temperature distribution, change of fiber tension and stress and strain distribution. Hahn et. al. [4] used foil gauges to measure radial pressure on the mandrel during winding. He found that the radial pressure stayed constant or even decreased slightly with subsequent winding layers over the first six layers as winding tension varies between 4 N and 23 N. Spencer [5] discovered that the flow of resin on radial direction results in the residual stress of filament winding production after curing. About the stress distribution of cured composite cylinders under several different loading conditions, Rizzo and Vicario [6] implemented a new elastic finite element program and showed that the stress distributions are effectively linear for

thickness/diameter < 0.1 , while for thickness/diameter > 0.1 they are nonlinear. When thickness/diameter < 0.02 , they can be solved by the classical shell theory. Ren [7] presented the exact solution for laminated cylindrical shell in cylindrical bending. Varadan et. al. [8] also found three-dimensional elasticity solutions for finite length, cross-ply cylindrical shells, which simply supported at both ends and subjected to transverse sinusoidal loading. The method improved the accuracy of results from classical shell theory.

To sum up, we find that processing parameters during winding are very important. Therefore, this research investigates the influence of two important processing parameters, fiber tension and resin viscosity, on the mechanical properties of composite cylinders wound with different winding angles. By controlling these two parameters, mechanical properties of composite cylinders wound with hybrid fibers, glass and carbon fibers, are also studied.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

(1) MATERIALS

(a) Resin:

Epoxy resin: NPEL-124, Na-Yah Co., Taiwan

Hardener: DICY, Ciba-Geigy Co., U. S. A.

Catalysts: DCMU, Aldrich Co., U. S. A.

(b) Fiber properties:

	Density ($\frac{g}{cm^3}$)	Fiber Diameter (μm)	Filaments/strand ($\times 1000$)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
Glass Fiber	2.54	13	12	72.4	3447
Carbon Fiber	1.78	7	12	234	4100

(2) FABRICATION

The composite cylinders are prepared by three-axis microcomputer controlled filament winding machine produced by CMC (Composite Machine Corporation, U. S. A.). A tension controller is designed and attached on the machine. The filament winding machine fabricates the composite cylinders with several different winding angles, 90, 60, and 45 degree, using CADWIND code which can control fiber path accurately. All the composite cylinders are wound with two layers. In the manufacturing process, the fiber strands are first passed through tension controller and dipped into resin bath which the temperature of resin (resin viscosity) can be controlled. Then the impregnated fiber strands are wound on the aluminium alloy mandrel with outer diameter 51 mm. Carbon, glass or hybrid fibers are impregnated with resin to obtain the semi-fabricated under controlled resin viscosity and fiber tension. After winding, the semi-fabricated composite cylinder is placed in a baking oven for curing. The cylinder must be rotated until the cylinder is cured. The cured cylinder is removed from the mandrel and cut as ring test specimen 6.4 mm in width and with inner diameter 51 mm.

(3) TEST METHODS

(a). Test equipment: Testometric MICRO 500 material testing machine

- (b). Fiber content measurement: For glass fiber content measurement, the specimen are placed in the high temperature oven and burned for six hours at 560 °C. The weight change of specimen results from lose of resin, therefore the fiber content can be calculated. The method for carbon fiber content measurement is the acid washing method suggested by ASTM D3173.
- (c). Tensile test: according to ASTM D2290.
- (d). Compressive test: according to Reference [9].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Not only the resin viscosity and fiber tension, but also winding angle and arrangement of fibers influence the mechanical properties of wound cylinders. They are discussed below.

(1) INFLUENCE OF VISCOSITY

The influences of resin viscosity on the mechanical properties of composite rings are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig 2. Owing to the increase of resin viscosity, the quantities of resin adhere to fiber strands increase. This makes the cured composites have better fiber protection and higher efficiency of load transfer. Therefore, they have both higher tensile strengths and compressive peak load. However, the increase of resin viscosity also slightly reduces fiber content and dimensional accuracy as shown in Table 1 and Table 2. Fig. 3 shows that most the tensile modulus of rings increases with the increase of resin viscosity. Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 show that delamination and fiber pull-out are major failure modes during tensile test, respectively.

(2) INFLUENCES OF FIBERS AND WINDING ANGLE

As shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 3, the tensile strength and tensile modulus of carbon/epoxy rings are higher than those of glass/epoxy rings when winding angle is 90 degree. This is because loads are carried mainly by fibers, and the tensile strength and the tensile modulus of carbon fiber are higher than those of glass fiber. The tensile modulus of carbon/epoxy rings with winding angles 60 and 45 degree are higer than that of glass/epoxy rings due to the same reason. However, the tensile strength of carbon/epoxy rings is almost the same as that of glass/epoxy rings, this is because the failure strain of carbon/epoxy rings is less than that of glass/epoxy rings. Although consolidation between glass/epoxy ring layers could be better than that of carbon/epoxy rings due to better stick of resin by glass fibers, no significant influence on tensile strength is observed.

For ring under compressive loading, failure results from compression plus bending fracture, where the inner fibers and outer fibers of the rings are subjected to compression and tension, respectively, and all the fibers subjected to additional uniform compression. The loading leads to the lower compressive strength of carbon/epoxy rings than that of glass/epoxy rings. It is observed that pull-out of outer fibers of ring (Fig. 6) and buckling of inner fibers of ring (Fig. 7) are caused by the bending moment. The results infer that carbon fibers with smaller diameter buckle easlier than glass fibers and reduce the compressive strength of rings of carbon/epoxy rings. For 60 and 45 degree composite rings under compressive load, shear stress occurs and must be transferred by resin matrix, hence, the glass/epoxy rings with higher resin stick have higher strength.

(3) INFLUENCE OF FIBER TENSION

Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show the mechanical properties of composite rings under different tensions 15 N and 50 N. The higher tension leads to the fibers of the outer layer moving toward the radial direction which squeezes the resin out of its original position. Therefore, the ring wound by higher fiber tension segregates the resin and fibers as shown in Fig. 10, where the fibers locate inside (upper portion) and the resin locates outside. The tensile strength of rings increases as fiber tension increases when winding angle is 90 degree as shown in Fig. 8. This is because most load is carried by fibers, therefore, the segregation of resin and fibers does not reduce the capability of the rings to carry tensile load.

With regard to the tensile strength of 60 and 45 degree rings and the compressive load of rings with three kinds of winding angles, they all decrease when fiber tension increases. The reason is due to higher resin stick on fiber and failure is dominated by shear stress. The segregation of fibers and resin also reduces the capability of load transfer between fibers. Besides, the increase of fiber tension also decreases the thickness of rings, improves the dimensional accuracy and increases the fiber content, as shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

(4) INFLUENCE OF HYBRID FIBERS

As shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, the tensile strength and maximum compressive load of hybrid composite rings are between those of carbon/epoxy rings and the glass/epoxy rings. In Table 3, the mechanical properties of the rings with glass fibers inside and carbon fibers outside are higher than those of rings with opposite arrangement. For ring under tension with glass fibers inside and carbon fibers outside, the strain of inner side of the ring (glass fiber) is greater than that of the outer side because the cross section of the ring is subjected to a tensile load plus a bending moment. Due to the lower fracture strain of carbon fiber compared to that of glass fiber, the composite ring can sustain higher stress before breaking which results in higher tensile strength. For ring under compression with same arrangement of glass and carbon fibers, the cross section of the ring is subjected to a compressive load plus a minus bending moment, glass fibers are under compression and carbon fibers under tension. This results in higher compressive strength of the ring because glass/epoxy rings have higher compressive strength and carbon/epoxy rings have high tensile strength as shown from previous results.

CONCLUSION

The increase of resin viscosity increases the mechanical properties of composite cylinders manufactured by filament winding, but it also decreases the dimensional accuracy of composite cylinder. The increase of fiber tension improves the tensile strength of wound composite cylinders when winding angle is 90 degree, however, it also reduces compressive strength of composite cylinders with winding angle 90 degree and mechanical properties of composite cylinders of 60 and 45 degrees. Composite cylinders wound by hybrid fibers show a medium strength in both tensile and compression tests as compared to glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy composite cylinders.

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Table 1 Comparison of the thickness of composite cylinders wound with different resin viscosities and fiber tensions

specimen	min. thickness (mm)	max. thickness (mm)	ave. thickness (mm)	specimen	min. thickness (mm)	max. thickness (mm)	ave. thickness (mm)
B901500E/G	1.03	1.17	1.09	A901500E/G	1.18	1.35	1.26
B601500E/G	1.43	1.57	1.51	A601500E/G	1.77	1.98	1.87
B60 500E/G	1.47	1.58	1.53	A60500E/G	1.74	1.91	1.87
B451500E/G	1.44	1.67	1.53	A451500E/G	1.76	1.95	1.83
B45 500E/G	1.47	1.51	1.47	A45500E/G	1.64	1.79	1.73
B901500E/C	1.05	1.15	1.09	A901500E/C	1.13	1.27	1.17
B90 500E/C	1.03	1.11	1.06	A90500 E/C	0.98	1.10	1.07
B601500E/C	0.99	1.10	1.05	A601500E/C	1.13	1.29	1.20
B60 500E/C	0.95	1.05	1.02	A60 500E/C	1.03	1.13	1.07
B451500E/C	1.05	1.20	1.13	A451500E/C	1.17	1.29	1.25
B45 500E/C	1.02	1.07	1.05	A45 500E/C	1.08	1.19	1.13

A: fiber tension 15 Nt, B: fiber tension 50 Nt, C: carbon fiber, E:epoxy resin,G: glass fiber, 90 - 60 - 45: winding angle, 1500 - 500: resin viscosity (unit: cps)

Table 2 Fiber content measurement

specimen	fiber volume ratio (%)	content weight ratio (%)	specimen	fiber volume ratio (%)	content weight ratio (%)
A901500E/G	47.63	67.66	A90 500E/C	46.47	60.91
A901000E/G	48.23	68.81	A45 500E/C	47.42	60.77
A90 500E/G	49.72	70.38	B901500E/G	50.28	71.53
A601500E/G	48.52	69.39	B601500E/G	52.79	73.91
A45 500E/G	47.82	67.76	B451500E/G	54.71	74.21
A901500E/C	38.86	53.13			

A: fiber tension 15 Nt, B: fiber tension 50 Nt, C:carbon fiber, E: epoxy resin, G:glass fiber, 90 - 60 - 45: winding angle, 1500 - 1000 - 500: resin viscosity(unit:cps)

Table 3 Comparison of mechanical properties of hybrid composite rings

specimen	min. thickness (mm)	max. thickness (mm)	ave. thickness (mm)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Peak load (Nt)
A90 1500E/H inner:carbon fiber outer:glass fiber	1.2	1.28	1.23	1218	227
A90 1500E/H inner:glass fiber outer:carbon fiber	1.22	1.31	1.25	1627	252

A: fiber tension 15 Nt, E:epoxy resin, H:hybrid fibers, 90:winding angle, 1500: resin viscosity(unit:cps)

Fig. 1 Comparison of the tensile strength of composite rings wound with glass, carbon, and hybrid fibers; fiber tension is 15 N; the range of experimental errors: 1%-13%.

Fig.2 Comparison of the compressive load of composite rings wound with glass, carbon and hybrid fibers;fiber tension is 15 N;the range of experimental errors: 2%-14%.

Fig. 3 Comparison of the tensile modulus of composite rings wound with glass, carbon, and hybrid fibers; fiber tension is 15 N; the range of experimental errors: 1%-13%.

Fig. 5 The composite ring with winding 60 degree showing fiber pull-out under tension.

Fig. 4 The composite ring with winding angle 60 degree showing delamination under tension.

Fig. 6 The composite ring with winding angle 90 degree showing fracture of outside fiber under compression.

Fig. 7(a) The composite ring with winding angle 90 degree showing fracture and buckling of inside fibers under compression.

Fig. 7(b) The composite ring with winding angle 90 degree showing inclined fracture surfaces of inside fibers under compression.

Fig. 8 Comparison of the tensile strength of glass/epoxy or carbon/epoxy ring wound with different fiber tension; the range of experimental errors : 1%-15%.

Fig. 9 Comparison of the compressive load of glass/epoxy or carbon/epoxy ring wound with different fiber tension; the range of experimental errors: 2%-20%.

Fig. 10. The composite ring wound with fiber tension 50 N showing separation of fibers and resin.